

COMPUTATIONAL RESOURCES FOR LLM COMPUTING: THE NEED FOR GPU VIRTUALIZATION

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With the rapid advancement of AI technologies like Large Language Models (LLMs), both training and deploying these models have become increasingly resource-intensive, particularly due to the heavy demands on hardware such as General-Purpose Graphics Processing Units (GPGPUs). Additionally, relying heavily on cloud infrastructures can lead to high operational costs and underutilized GPU resources. To tackle these challenges, recent research has investigated GPU virtualization as a promising approach to enhance flexibility and optimize resource utilization. In this paper, we begin by examining the growing demand for resources in LLM training and inference workloads, followed by an analysis of various virtualization techniques, highlighting their benefits and limitations. Next, we describe the details of our open-source GPU virtualization framework GVirtuS, its components and the way how it deals with executing CUDA functions on behalf of devices or VMs without direct access to a GPU. Our results demonstrate that GVirtuS can deliver up to a 2× speed-up for LLM inference compared to CPU-only processing. As part of our EU Chips-JU project CLEVER, this work aims to explore the potential of our GVirtuS framework for broader applications in GPU virtualization and AI workloads in the future.

Keywords: Large Language Models, AI, Inference, GPU virtualization, HPC

1 Introduction

Large Language Models (LLMs) represent a transformative milestone in the development of artificial intelligence (AI). Unlike earlier rule-based systems and smaller statistical models, LLMs based on transformer architectures can process massive amounts of text, learn complex patterns, and generate coherent, human-like responses (Floridi et al., 2020). They are capable of performing tasks such as question answering, summarization, translation, coding assistance, and conversational interaction (Touvron, Lavril, et al., 2023), which has fueled the rapid growth of generative AI applications across research, industry, and everyday life. The versatility of LLMs arises from their scale, since models with hundreds of billions or even trillions of parameters are able to generalize across diverse tasks without task-specific training (Sathish et al., 2024). This combination of capability and adaptability has positioned LLMs as a key driver of innovation, but it also comes with unprecedented technical and resource demands.

Training and deploying models with billions of parameters demand massive processing power and storage capacity, often making graphics processing units (GPUs) the most critical and costly component in modern computing infrastructures. GPUs have traditionally been allocated as entire devices to a single job or tenant, even when workloads utilize only a fraction of the

available compute or memory capacity. Recent advances such as NVIDIA Multi-Instance GPU (MIG) (NVIDIA Corporation, 2023) enable multiple workloads to share a device, but these mechanisms remain coarse-grained, hardware-specific, and limited in flexibility. Such rigid provisioning leads to wasted GPU capacity, higher operational costs, and reduced concurrency across jobs (Ye et al., 2024). For service providers, this under-utilization directly translates into higher expenses, while for researchers and developers it restricts access to already scarce GPU resources. These inefficiencies constrain the scalability and effectiveness of LLM training and inference at a time when demand for such models is rapidly increasing.

To address these challenges, GPU virtualization has emerged as a promising solution. By abstracting physical devices and enabling multiple users or workloads to share the same GPU, virtualization improves resource efficiency, lowers costs, and broadens access to GPU acceleration on resource-constrained devices. Approaches such as API remoting, para- and full virtualization, and hardware-supported methods each involve different trade-offs between performance, flexibility, and ease of deployment. These techniques not only increase utilization but also enable new deployment scenarios, ranging from serverless execution platforms to heterogeneous clusters and lightweight edge systems. In this paper, we examine the applicability of existing GPU virtualization frameworks to LLM workloads and analyze their limitations. Our contributions are threefold:

- We review the resource requirements of various LLMs, including both training and inference stages.
- We illustrate how GPU virtualization techniques can be integrated to alleviate resource constraints in both stages of LLM pipelines.
- We analyze current GPU virtualization methods, discussing their potential for GPU sharing as well as their limitations.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the main approaches to GPU virtualization and outlines their architectural principles. Section 3 reviews prior efforts that apply GPU virtualization in both AI and scientific computing domains. Section 4 examines the resource demands of LLMs and highlights the challenges associated with their training and inference. Section 5 discusses the potential benefits of leveraging GPU virtualization for LLM workloads, while also analyzing its current limitations. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the key findings and suggests directions for future research.

2 Background

GPU virtualization techniques can be broadly classified into three categories according to their implementation strategy, each with a distinct architectural approach. Figure 1 illustrates representative system designs for each category.

2.1 API Remoting

A common approach is API remoting, shown in Figure 1(a), where the guest operating system is provided with a wrapper library that replicates the interface of the native GPU API. Instead of executing calls locally, the wrapper intercepts GPU function calls issued by applications, such as CUDA API calls, and redirects them to a front-end driver. The front-end is responsible for serializing the operation parameters, including kernel code, input data, and configuration settings, into a transferable message. This message is then forwarded over a network to a back-end component in the host operating system, which has direct access to the physical CUDA devices. The back-end driver deserializes the message, reconstructs the original GPU call, and executes the requested operation on the physical GPU. The results, including any output data or return codes, are then sent back to the front-end, which returns them to the application through the wrapper. Several API remoting methods have been developed, including rCUDA (Duato et al., 2010), GVirtuS (Giunta et al., 2010), FairGV (Hong et al., 2017) and Cricket (Eiling et al., 2022). This approach has demonstrated the potential to overcome the limitations of black-box GPU drivers by enabling virtualization at the library level.

2.2 Para- and Full Virtualization

Another category is para- and full virtualization, as illustrated in Figure 1(b), which operates at the driver level. In driver-level GPU virtualization, application requests are forwarded from the guest driver to a QEMU-emulated GPU device via shared memory. The device maintains the state of each virtual GPU and queues requests, which are then scheduled and executed on the physical GPU, with results returned to the application. In para-virtualization (Gottschlag et al., 2013; Huang et al., 2016), the guest OS uses a slightly modified custom driver that forwards sensitive operations directly to the host driver. In contrast, full virtualization (Tian et al., 2014; Hsu et al., 2016) fully emulates the GPU for the guest OS, allowing unmodified drivers and applications to run transparently. This approach demonstrates the ability to maintain compatibility with existing GPU libraries while enabling hypervisor-level features such as monitoring and live migration.

2.3 Hardware-Supported Virtualization

A third approach is hardware-supported virtualization, shown in Figure 1(c). It uses technologies such as Intel VT-d or AMD-Vi to let a virtual machine access the GPU directly, without changing its drivers or libraries. This method is also known as GPU passthrough or single-root I/O virtualization (SR-IOV). In this setup, the guest OS communicates with the GPU without going through the hypervisor. Because these extensions allow only one VM to use a GPU at a time, hot-plug methods have been proposed to let different VMs take turns by dynamically attaching or removing the GPU. These hardware features for I/O virtualization are provided by CPU and GPU vendors (NVIDIA Corporation, 2023). This method has demonstrated the ability to achieve GPU virtualization with hardware support, delivering near-native performance without additional software layers.

(a) API remoting approach.

(b) Para- or full virtualization approach.

(c) Hardware-supported approach.

Figure 1: Architecture of different GPU virtualization approaches and their components.

3 Related Work

Research on GPU virtualization has explored diverse strategies to improve flexibility, portability, and computational efficiency in AI, scientific computing, and large-scale data processing. One important line of work focuses on API remoting, a technique that allows applications to access GPU resources transparently even when the physical GPU is located remotely or resides on a heterogeneous system. This approach is particularly valuable in scenarios where lightweight clients, edge devices, or legacy systems lack dedicated GPUs but still need to execute highly parallel workloads.

(Montella et al., 2018) demonstrate that GVirtuS can accelerate seafloor depth interpolation algorithms used in crowdsourced marine bathymetry, enabling GPU-based computation even on devices lacking dedicated accelerators. The study shows that GPU-accelerated computation can be extended to devices that traditionally operate without GPUs, enabling broader participation in scientific workflows and lowering hardware requirements for end users. (Wang et al., 2024) evaluate the Cricket framework for AI workloads such as ResNet and BERT. Their results show that latency, bandwidth, and request granularity strongly influence the efficiency of remote GPU execution, and that different neural architectures exhibit varying tolerance to API-remoting overheads. These findings underscore the importance of both workload characteristics and communication patterns in the design of remoting-based systems.

Another widely used API remoting framework is rCUDA. (Naranjo et al., 2020) apply rCUDA to enable serverless execution of a deep learning model for segmentation and classification of

transthoracic echocardiography images. The results show that while direct GPU access delivers the highest performance, rCUDA still achieves notable speedups compared to CPU-only execution and, importantly, enables parallelism by allowing multiple serverless functions to share a single GPU. Similarly, (Satheesh Kumar et al., 2024) employ rCUDA to accelerate a bi-directional recurrent neural network for video compression and report consistent performance improvements across all terms of evaluation metrics compared to state-of-the-art methods.

Beyond API-level solutions, virtualization has been explored at the driver and hardware levels to improve resource utilization in cloud and multi-tenant environments. (Michael et al., 2020) evaluate High Performance Computing (HPC) and deep learning workloads on NVIDIA vGPU solutions, comparing benchmarks such as High Performance Linpack and MLPerf Training across both native and virtualized environments. Results show that the performance penalty is generally below 10% for HPC tasks, whereas deep learning benchmarks exhibit task-dependent variability. (Mohan et al., 2025) introduce Vela, a KVM-based framework that combines GPU passthrough with a virtualized RDMA over Converged Ethernet (ROCE) network to support multi-tenant LLM training with strong scalability. The framework enables flexible deployment in cloud environments while maintaining efficient resource sharing. Experimental evaluation reveals that Vela sustains about 80% of the ideal throughput when training a 50-billion-parameter decoder model with model parallelism, and around 70% of per-GPU FLOPS compared to a single VM running the High Performance Linpack benchmark.

4 Resource Demands of Large Language Models

The rapid evolution of LLMs has fundamentally transformed natural language understanding and generation, yet it has also exposed critical bottlenecks in computational scalability and infrastructure efficiency. As model sizes continue to grow from millions to trillions of parameters, the corresponding demand for compute, memory, and energy resources has increased exponentially. Training and deploying these models now require access to large-scale GPU clusters, specialized interconnects, and vast storage systems, creating unprecedented challenges for both researchers and industry practitioners. Beyond the sheer hardware requirements, the operational costs, power consumption, and environmental footprint of LLMs have become major considerations in sustainable AI development. This section examines the computational, memory, and cost requirements of modern LLMs and explores the challenges associated with their execution in large-scale and cloud-based environments, providing a

foundation for understanding the need for more efficient resource utilization strategies such as GPU virtualization.

4.1 Computational and Memory Needs of LLMs

LLMs such as GPT-3 (Floridi et al., 2020), PaLM (Anil et al., 2023), and LLaMA-2 (Touvron, Martin, et al., 2023) have demonstrated state-of-the-art performance across a wide range of natural language processing tasks, including text generation, reasoning, knowledge retrieval, and coding assistance. Their success has driven a rapid shift toward ever-larger architectures, with model scale becoming a key determinant of accuracy and generalization. However, these advances come at an unprecedented cost in both computation and memory resources, raising significant challenges for large-scale deployment, reproducibility, and sustainable AI research. Training LLMs involves scaling to billions or even trillions of parameters, which translates into massive compute budgets. For example, training GPT-3, with 175B parameters, has been estimated to require nearly 333,000 GPU-hours on NVIDIA A100 accelerators, a level of computation that corresponds to several million dollars in cloud or cluster resources. Similarly, training LLaMA-2 with 13B parameters consumed more than 368,000 GPU-hours (Sathish et al., 2024). These numbers highlight the prohibitive resource investment needed to push model sizes forward.

Unlike training, inference must be optimized for low latency, cost-efficient serving, and predictable performance under real-world workloads. For instance, GPT-3 requires storing 175 billion 16-bit parameters, which amounts to roughly 350 GB of memory, and running inference typically needs at least five NVIDIA A100 GPUs to satisfy typical latency targets for interactive applications. In contrast, inference for LLaMA-2 can often be supported by a single modern GPU, making them significantly more practical for deployment across diverse settings such as consumer devices, edge platforms, and lightweight cloud environments. This illustrates how training cost scales much more steeply with parameters compared to inference cost, though deployments still present major memory bottlenecks at larger scales.

Table 4.a summarizes the estimated costs of training and inference for several well-known LLMs in cloud environments. The reported values illustrate the immense computational expense of these models, with training costs ranging from a few million dollars for models such as T5 and BLOOM to nearly 100 million dollars for GPT-4. Similarly, daily inference or serving costs vary widely, from just a few dollars for smaller models to as much as \$900 per instance for large-scale deployments, underscoring the significant financial burden associated with sustaining high-performance LLM services. These figures emphasize not only the

technical burden but also the significant economic barrier associated with state-of-the-art LLMs, reinforcing the need for more efficient model architectures, optimized serving strategies, and resource-efficient execution environments.

Table 4.a: Details of LLMs and their associated costs. Adapted from (Sathish et al., 2024).

<i>Model</i>	<i>Size (Params)</i>	<i>Cost</i>	
		Train (Mil\$)	Inference (\$/day)
<i>T5 (Raffel et al., 2020)</i>	11B	2	36
<i>LLaMA-2 (Touvron, Martin, et al., 2023)</i>	7B	5.52	18
<i>GPT-3 (Floridi et al., 2020)</i>	175B	5	180
<i>BLOOM (Scao et al., 2022)</i>	176B	5	180
<i>PaLM (Anil et al., 2023)</i>	540B	23.1	500
<i>GPT-4 (Achiam et al., 2023)</i>	1000B	100	900

4.2 Challenges of LLM Execution on Cloud Platforms

Due to their extreme computational and memory requirements, most state-of-the-art LLMs are deployed and served through cloud infrastructures. Cloud platforms provide clusters of GPUs or Tensor Processing Units (TPUs) with elastic scalability and high performance needed to train and serve such models at scale. Examples of this trend include OpenAI’s GPT-3 and GPT-4, which are trained and served through Microsoft Azure (Floridi et al., 2020; Achiam et al., 2023), and Google’s Gemini models, which are trained on TPU pods on datacenters and deployed within Google Cloud (Gemini Team et al., 2023). However, this dependence on the cloud introduces several challenges.

Although modern cloud platforms support GPU sharing mechanisms, these features alone are often insufficient, as they can lack the isolation, flexibility, and performance predictability required for secure and stable multi-tenant environments. When multiple users or workloads share a single GPU, there is a persistent risk of the noisy-neighbor problem, where a resource-intensive job from one tenant can monopolize compute, memory bandwidth, or interconnect capacity, resulting in significant performance degradation for others. This contention can manifest in several ways: a job might consume all available memory bandwidth, block access to the PCIe bus, or saturate the GPU’s compute cores.

Furthermore, existing GPU sharing mechanisms often rely on hardware-specific features and fixed partitioning schemes, which limit their flexibility for diverse workloads. In practice, jobs such as inference for medium-sized models or fine-tuning with small batch sizes may still leave portions of GPU compute or memory underutilized, since the allocated partition cannot always be fully saturated by the workload (Gao et al., 2024; Han et al., 2022). For example, in (Narayanan et al., 2021), they show that distributed LLM training often suffers from idle device time, where some GPUs stall while waiting for synchronization barriers, whereas others operate far below their theoretical utilization due to communication bottlenecks or imbalanced work distribution. These inefficiencies are further amplified by the key–value (KV) cache used for transformer attention, which grows dynamically with sequence length and request concurrency. Because most serving systems store each request’s KV cache in contiguous memory regions, memory fragmentation arises, making it difficult to efficiently pack KV caches of different lengths. This fragmentation prevents effective sharing of GPU memory across requests, ultimately limiting concurrency and throughput (Kwon et al., 2023).

5 Potential Role of GPU Virtualization

The exponential growth of LLMs has intensified the need for scalable and efficient computational infrastructures. GPU virtualization emerges as a promising strategy to address these challenges by enabling shared and flexible use of accelerator resources across multiple users, processes, or virtual machines. Through virtualization, GPU capabilities can be dynamically partitioned, remoted, or abstracted to suit different workloads, improving utilization while maintaining isolation and performance guarantees. This section explores the potential of GPU virtualization to enhance LLM deployment efficiency, outlining its core approaches and practical implications for inference and training scalability.

5.1 The Promise of GPU Virtualization

GPU virtualization provides a practical mechanism to improve utilization and reduce the prohibitive costs of large-scale LLM training and inference. By virtualizing the GPU, compute and memory resources can be allocated with greater flexibility, adapting dynamically to the requirements of each workload. At the same time, virtualization ensures strong isolation between tenants, preventing faults or security vulnerabilities in one workload from impacting others running on the same device. Broadly, three strategies are employed: API remoting, para/full virtualization, and hardware-assisted virtualization. Each approach brings distinct benefits and opens new possibilities for deploying LLMs efficiently across a variety of environments.

API Remoting. This approach gains elastic scaling across nodes. It supports remote GPU access from the local machine, allowing CPU-only servers, lightweight edge devices, and multi-tenant platforms to transparently benefit from GPU acceleration. For LLMs, API remoting is particularly appealing because unused GPU memory from one client can be reassigned to another’s KV cache, helping mitigate memory fragmentation and improving overall utilization across variable-length requests.

Para- and Full Virtualization. Virtualized drivers allow GPU memory to be partitioned among tenants, reducing idle capacity when workloads only consume part of the device. These approaches are especially effective for lightweight services, such as chatbot-style deployments with small batch sizes, that might otherwise leave significant portions of the GPU underutilized. In addition, the hypervisor layer provides stronger control over noisy-neighbor interference compared to direct sharing, ensuring more predictable performance in multi-tenant environments.

Hardware-Supported Virtualization. This approach leverages built-in hardware features to enable GPU virtualization without the overhead of an additional software layer. It provides deterministic resource allocation, ensuring strong isolation and predictable quality of service across tenants. For LLM workloads, hardware-supported methods allow multiple models to run concurrently on the same device while aligning GPU resources more closely with actual workload demands. As a result, they minimize resource waste and improve the cost-effectiveness of large-scale deployments.

5.2 GPU Virtualization performance in LLM

To evaluate the feasibility of GPU virtualization for LLM inference, we selected the GPU Virtualization Service (GVirtuS) as the focus of our study. GVirtuS stands out as a fully open-source, containerized framework capable of supporting CUDA-based workloads without requiring any modification to the application code. Its modular architecture and compatibility with modern GPU drivers make it particularly suitable for investigating the potential of virtualized GPU acceleration in LLM computation.

5.2.1 GVirtuS

GVirtuS (Giunta et al., 2010) is an API remoting framework that enables transparent access to accelerator libraries such as CUDA and OpenCL. By abstracting the physical GPU through a remote interface, GVirtuS allows applications running in virtualized or isolated environments to execute GPU operations as if the GPU is locally attached. This approach ensures that applications do not need to be rewritten to take advantage of remote GPU acceleration.

Additionally, GVirtuS supports the CUDA 12.6 API, which provides compatibility with the latest GPU architectures and PyTorch builds.

The architecture of GVirtuS shown in Figure 2 is based on a split-driver model, consisting of two primary components: the front-end and the back-end. The front-end is responsible for interfacing directly with the application. It provides a wrapper CUDA library that replicates the NVIDIA CUDA interface, intercepting all CUDA API calls made by the application. Once intercepted, these calls are collected, and all relevant parameters are serialized into structured packets. Each packet contains comprehensive information required to perform the requested operation remotely, including kernel identifiers, memory addresses, execution parameters, and input data if necessary. This design allows GVirtuS to redirect CUDA calls transparently, without requiring any modifications to the original application code.

Figure 2: Overview of the GVirtuS components and system architecture.

Between the front-end and the back-end, the communicator acts as a transport and synchronization layer. All serialized CUDA packets and their corresponding results are transmitted through this component. The communicator is responsible for establishing reliable, bidirectional communication channels, ensuring that CUDA calls and responses are delivered correctly and in the proper order. It also manages synchronization between the guest (front-end) and host (back-end), maintaining data consistency and integrity during execution. GVirtuS provides multiple communicator implementations, which can use TCP/IP, RDMA, or other communication mechanisms depending on the deployment scenario. The back-end operates on the host machine, running as a privileged service capable of directly interacting with the native CUDA driver. Once a packet is received from the communicator, the back-end deserializes it, executes the requested CUDA operation on the GPU, and returns the results to the front-end through the communicator. This modular separation of concerns allows the front-end to remain lightweight, with no direct dependency on the physical GPU, while the back-end handles all GPU execution and resource management.

5.2.2 GVirtuS Performance on LLMs

To evaluate the effectiveness of GVirtuS, we conducted experiments on three different setups. The first setup uses a native GPU configuration with an NVIDIA RTX A5000, featuring 8,192 CUDA cores and 24 GB of GDDR6 memory. This setup represents the optimal scenario where the application has direct access to a high-performance GPU. The second setup is CPU-only, equipped with an AMD EPYC 7702P processor running at 2.0 GHz, with 64 cores, 256 MB of L3 cache, and 512 GB of DDR4 RAM. This setup represents a scenario in which GPU resources are unavailable, and all computations must rely solely on the CPU. The third setup leverages GVirtuS to combine these two machines: the front-end runs on the EPYC CPU-only workstation, while the back-end runs on the RTX A5000 GPU workstation, with communication handled via a TCP/IP communicator to enable remote GPU access efficiently. For the experimental evaluation, two state-of-the-art LLMs are selected: Qwen3-1.7B (Yang et al., 2025) and Gemma3-1B (Gemma Team, 2025). These models are chosen for their moderate parameter sizes, balanced computational demands, and strong inference performance, making them suitable for benchmarking on a workstation-scale setup. Each model is prompted with the same input data, and the generation of time per response is measured as the primary performance metric. To ensure statistical reliability, each configuration is executed 100 times, and both the mean and standard deviation of execution times are recorded. This repetition reduces the influence of transient system conditions such as background processes, network fluctuations, and caching effects, providing a more consistent and reproducible performance comparison.

Figure 3 presents the mean execution times and its standard deviation for all three configurations. The native GPU setup unsurprisingly achieves the lowest latency and highest throughput, serving as the theoretical upper bound of performance. The CPU-only configuration produces the slowest execution times, demonstrating the computational limitations of running transformer-based models entirely on general-purpose processors. In contrast, the GVirtuS setup achieves a substantial performance improvement compared to the CPU-only configuration, with speedups exceeding threefold for both LLMs under identical workloads and input conditions.

Figure 3: LLMs test. Performance comparison of two LLMs across three different hardware setups after 100 execution runs. The mean execution time and standard deviation for Qwen3-1.7B are 36.25 ± 5.16 seconds on the CPU-only setup, 7.01 ± 0.86 seconds using GVirtuS, and 3.20 ± 0.41 seconds on the native GPU. For Gemma3-1B, the CPU-only execution requires 64.66 ± 10.58 seconds; GVirtuS takes 17.25 ± 2.44 seconds, and the native GPU completes the task in 2.54 ± 0.96 seconds.

In summary, the experimental findings demonstrate that GVirtuS can bridge the performance gap between CPU-only and GPU-enabled environments, achieving meaningful acceleration even over standard network connections. Although it does not fully match native GPU performance, the reduction in inference time and the high stability of execution highlight its practical value. With further optimizations, GVirtuS could achieve even closer performance to native GPU execution. Overall, these results confirm that GPU virtualization offers a promising pathway to enhance accessibility, scalability, and efficiency in LLM deployment and research.

5.3 GPU Virtualization shortages and open challenges

Despite these benefits, current approaches to GPU virtualization face important trade-offs and open challenges when applied to LLMs.

API remoting introduces additional layers of communication and network overhead, which can significantly impact performance, particularly in latency-sensitive inference workloads. Since each GPU call must be serialized, transmitted, and deserialized across the network, the added latency can accumulate during frequent kernel launches or memory transfers. This

overhead can create bottlenecks in large-scale distributed training environments where synchronization across multiple nodes is required. Nonetheless, API remoting remains attractive for scenarios where hardware flexibility and remote GPU sharing are prioritized over absolute performance, such as in research or multi-tenant systems.

Para- and Full Virtualization enable resource sharing and memory partitioning among multiple virtual machines, allowing more efficient GPU utilization. However, these methods introduce higher emulation costs and additional driver-level complexity compared to hardware-assisted approaches. As a result, they are less suited for computationally demanding workloads, such as full-scale LLM training, where performance and low-level access to GPU resources are critical. Instead, these techniques are often better suited for lightweight inference, model serving, or fine-tuning tasks, where partial GPU access can still provide meaningful acceleration without requiring exclusive device ownership.

Hardware-Supported Virtualization achieves near-native performance by leveraging GPU-level features such as MIG or SR-IOV technology. These approaches enable hardware-level isolation and direct access to GPU resources, minimizing the virtualization overhead seen in software-based methods. However, their reliance on vendor-specific implementations limits portability and locks systems into proprietary hardware ecosystems. This dependency can restrict flexibility for heterogeneous environments and pose challenges for open-source or cross-platform deployment.

Beyond the limitations of different GPU virtualization methods, there are broader concerns when applying these techniques to LLM workloads. Multi-tenant interference remains a significant risk, as co-located jobs can contend for shared GPU resources, such as compute units, memory bandwidth, and interconnects, potentially degrading quality-of-service for latency-sensitive LLM inference and throughput-critical training. This is particularly problematic in large-scale deployments, where small fluctuations in GPU performance across tenants can cascade into straggler effects and synchronization delays. Furthermore, existing virtualization frameworks struggle with dynamic memory requirements, such as the growing KV caches in LLMs, which lead to fragmentation and limit concurrency. Addressing this gap will require rethinking GPU scheduling, memory management for KV caches, and integration with distributed training frameworks. Many current virtualization frameworks are designed for HPC or general AI workloads, not for trillion-parameter LLMs, which introduces a mismatch between existing capabilities and the requirements of next-generation models. The sheer scale and complexity of LLMs, with their unique memory access patterns and computational demands, necessitate novel virtualization solutions tailored to their specific needs.

6 Conclusion

The rapid progress of LLMs has amplified the demand for efficient use of GPU resources. This paper highlights the current challenges posed by the massive scale of these models, which require substantial resources for both training and deployment. While the cloud provides the scale and elasticity needed to train and deploy LLMs, it also introduces challenges such as high cost, resource idleness, memory pressure, and performance variability. GPU virtualization emerges as a promising strategy to mitigate these issues by enabling sharing accelerators, improving deployment flexibility, and supporting multi-tenancy. Our review highlights three major approaches, API remoting, para- and full virtualization, and hardware-supported virtualization. Each approach offers distinct benefits and trade-offs. API remoting improves the flexibility for memory allocation and GPU limited device. However, it suffers from network overhead; para- and full virtualization supports sharing and reduce idle capacity but add driver-level complexity and overhead; and hardware-supported GPU virtualization achieves more efficient packing of GPU resources yet remain tied to proprietary hardware ecosystems.

To further explore the potential of GPU virtualization in practical LLM inference scenarios, we implement and evaluate GVirtuS, an API remoting framework that provides virtualized GPU access. GVirtuS operates through a split-driver design, with a front-end component intercepting application-level CUDA calls and a back-end component executing them on a physical GPU. These two components communicate through a dedicated communicator layer, which handles data transmission, synchronization, and result delivery. Experimental results using Qwen3-1.7B and Gemma3-1B models demonstrate that GVirtuS substantially reduces execution time compared to CPU-only inference, achieving performance improvements of more than threefold. Although the performance remains below that of native GPU execution, primarily due to network and serialization overhead, GVirtuS nonetheless proves effective in enabling GPU acceleration from remote or CPU-only environments.

Despite the clear benefits of these approaches, several challenges remain unresolved when applying GPU virtualization to LLM workloads. Multi-tenant interference is a persistent concern, as co-located jobs may compete for compute units, memory bandwidth, and interconnect capacity. Such contention can degrade quality of service, particularly for latency-sensitive inference and throughput-intensive training tasks. Existing frameworks also struggle with dynamic memory requirements such as growing KV caches, which lead to fragmentation and limit concurrency. Furthermore, many current solutions are not designed with trillion-parameter models in mind, highlighting a gap between today’s virtualization capabilities and the requirements of next-generation AI systems. As part of ongoing initiatives such as the EU

Chips-JU CLEVER project, future work will explore extending frameworks like GVirtuS to better meet the unique demands of LLMs, bridging the gap between current virtualization capabilities and the next generation of AI systems.

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